

1 **A genetically encoded inhibitor of 53BP1 to stimulate homology-based gene**
2 **editing**

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4 Marella D. Canny^{1*}, Nathalie Moatti^{1*}, Leo C.K. Wan^{1,2}, Amélie Fradet-Turcotte^{1,3}, Danielle
5 Krasner⁴, Pedro A. Mateos-Gomez⁵, Michal Zimmermann¹, Alexandre Orthwein^{1,6}, Yu-Chi
6 Juang¹, Wei Zhang⁷, Sylvie M. Noordermeer¹, Eduardo Seclen Hidalgo⁴, Marcus D. Wilson¹,
7 Andrew Vorobyov⁵, Meagan Munro¹, Andreas Ernst^{7,8}, , Timothy F. Ng^{1,2}, Tiffany Cho^{1,2}, Paula
8 Cannon⁴, Sachdev S. Sidhu^{2,5}, Frank Sicheri^{1,2} and Daniel Durocher^{1,2,¶}

9

10 ¹The Lunenfeld-Tanenbaum Research Institute, Mount Sinai Hospital, 600 University Avenue,
11 Toronto, ON, M5G 1X5, Canada

12 ²Department of Molecular Genetics, University of Toronto, ON, M5S 3E1, Canada.

13 ³Present address: St-Patrick Research Group in Basic Oncology, Université Laval Cancer
14 Research Center, and Oncology Axis-CHU de Québec Research Center – Université Laval,
15 Quebec City, QC, G1R 2J6, Canada

16 ⁴Department of Molecular Microbiology and Immunology, Keck School of Medicine, University
17 of Southern California, Los Angeles, CA, USA

18 ⁵Skirball Institute of Biomolecular Medicine, Department of Cell Biology, NYU Langone
19 Medical Center, New York, NY 10016

20 ⁶Present address: Department of Oncology, McGill University, Montreal, QC, H3G 0G4, Canada
21 and Segal Cancer Center, Jewish General Hospital, Lady Davis Institute for Medical Research,
22 Montreal, QC, H3T 1E2, Canada

23 ⁷The Donnelly Centre for Cellular and Biomolecular Research, Banting and Best Department of
24 Medical Research, University of Toronto, ON, M5S 3E1, Canada

25 ⁸Present address: Institute of Biochemistry II, Goethe University School of Medicine, Theodor-
26 Stern-Kai 7, 60590, Frankfurt am Main, Germany.

27

28 *These authors contributed equally

29

30 ¶Address correspondence to:

31 Daniel Durocher, Ph.D.
32 The Lunenfeld-Tanenbaum Research Institute
33 Mount Sinai Hospital, Room 1073
34 600 University Avenue
35 Toronto, ON M5G 1X5
36 CANADA
37 Tel: 416-586-4800 ext. 2544
38 e-mail: durocher@lunenfeld.ca
39

40 The expanding repertoire of programmable nucleases such as Cas9 brings new
41 opportunities in genetic medicine¹⁻³. In many cases, these nucleases are engineered to
42 induce a DNA double-strand break (DSB) to stimulate precise genome editing by
43 homology-dependent repair (HDR). However, HDR is hindered by competing DSB repair
44 pathways such as non-homologous end-joining (NHEJ)⁴. Here, we report the development
45 of a genetically encoded inhibitor of 53BP1 (coded by *TP53BP1*), a regulator of DSB repair
46 pathway choice^{4, 5}. 53BP1 promotes NHEJ over HDR by suppressing end resection, the
47 formation of 3' single-stranded DNA tails, which is the rate-limiting step in the initiation of
48 HDR. The inhibitor of 53BP1 (or i53) was identified through the screening of a massive
49 combinatorial library of engineered ubiquitin variants by phage display⁶. i53 binds and
50 occludes the ligand binding site of the 53BP1 Tudor domain with high affinity and
51 selectivity, blocking its ability to accumulate at sites of DNA damage. i53 is a potent and
52 selective inhibitor of 53BP1 that enhances gene targeting and chromosomal gene
53 conversion in human or mouse cells with either double-stranded DNA or single-stranded
54 oligonucleotide donors. i53 is effective when delivered from plasmid, mRNA or adeno-
55 associated virus. We conclude that 53BP1 inhibition is a robust tool to enhance HDR-based
56 precise genome editing.

57
58 In human cells, the dominant pathway that mends two-ended DSBs, such as those created by
59 programmable nucleases is NHEJ. NHEJ limits HDR first by being a fast-acting repair pathway
60 that re-seals broken ends through a DNA ligase IV-dependent reaction⁷. Secondly, the
61 Ku70/Ku80 heterodimer binds to DNA ends with high affinity, blocking their processing by the
62 nucleases that generate the single-stranded DNA (ssDNA) tails that are necessary for the

63 initiation of HR^{7, 8}. A chromatin-based ubiquitin (Ub)-dependent signaling cascade⁹ is also
64 initiated by the detection of DSBs that modulates DSB repair pathway “choice”¹⁰. This pathway
65 is largely controlled by a poorly understood antagonism between 53BP1, a pro-NHEJ factor, and
66 BRCA1, the well-known breast and ovarian tumor suppressor and HR factor¹⁰. 53BP1 limits HR
67 in part by blocking long-range DNA end resection but also by inhibiting BRCA1 recruitment to
68 DSB sites^{11, 12}.

69 To identify inhibitors of 53BP1, we took advantage of a soft-randomized library of
70 ubiquitin variants (Ubvs)⁶ that was initially developed to identify inhibitors of ubiquitin-binding
71 proteins such as deubiquitylases. Since 53BP1 recognizes histone H2A ubiquitylated on Lys15
72 (H2AK15ub) in order to accumulate at DSB sites¹³, we reasoned that it might be possible to
73 identify Ubvs targeting the 53BP1 UDR, the domain involved in ubiquitylated histone
74 recognition¹³. After 5 rounds of selection against a GST-53BP1 fragment containing the tandem
75 Tudor domain and the ubiquitin-dependent recruitment or UDR (residues 1484-1631; [Fig. 1a](#)),
76 10 unique phages were selected for re-testing in ELISA assays for binding to the Tudor-UDR
77 region of 53BP1 and 14 other proteins, most of them known ubiquitin-binding proteins ([Fig. 1b](#)).
78 This process identified 5 distinct Ubvs that bound selectively to 53BP1 (A10, A11, C08, G08
79 and H04; [Fig. 1bc](#)). We then generated GST fusion proteins to 4 of these 5 Ubvs and tested them
80 in GST pulldown assays against maltose-binding protein (MBP) fused to either the Tudor
81 domain (residues 1484-1603) or the Tudor-UDR fragment of 53BP1. To our surprise, we
82 observed that in addition to binding the UDR-containing protein, each Ubv bound to the MBP
83 fusion containing only the 53BP1 Tudor domain ([Fig. 1de](#)). Since the UDR is apparently not
84 required for binding to the Ubv, all further experiments were carried out with proteins containing
85 solely the Tudor domain. We selected clone G08 for further analysis because the phage

86 expressing it displayed strongest binding by ELISA (Fig. 1b) and contained only 7 mutations, the
87 lowest number of amino acid substitutions among the selected Ubvs (Fig. 1c).

88 Since the 53BP1 Tudor domain binds to dimethylated histone H4 Lys20 (H4K20me2)¹⁴,
89 we tested whether UbvG08- and H4K20me2-binding functions were mutually exclusive. We
90 found that H4K20me2 peptides competed UbvG08 for 53BP1 binding with a half-maximal
91 competing concentration in the 100 μ M to 300 μ M range (Fig. 1f). Since the dissociation constant
92 (K_d) of the H4K20me2 peptide-53BP1 Tudor interaction is 20 μ M¹⁴, the result of the H4K20me2
93 peptide competition implied that 53BP1 bound to UbvG08 with much higher affinity than
94 methyl-lysine peptides. Indeed, as assessed by isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC), UbvG08
95 bound to the 53BP1 Tudor domain with K_d of 242 \pm 52 nM ($N=3$), two orders of magnitude
96 tighter than the 53BP1-H4K20me2 interaction (Fig. 1g). In contrast, a version of UbvG08 that
97 reverted the L69P and V70L mutations to wild type (mutant DM; see below for the rationale
98 behind these mutations) did not display any detectable binding to the 53BP1 Tudor domain by
99 ITC (Fig. 1g).

100 To gain insight into the mechanism by which UbvG08 binds to 53BP1, we solved the
101 crystal structure of UbvG08 bound to the 53BP1 Tudor domain (see Methods for protein
102 expression, crystallization, and structure determination details). Within the solved complex, the
103 Tudor domain of 53BP1 adopted a canonical mixed α - β fold identical to that reported in its apo
104 state (1XNI; secondary structure RMSD of 1.0 \AA) and in complex with a H4K20me2 derived
105 peptide (2IG0; secondary structure RMSD of 1.1 \AA) (Supplementary Fig. 1a). UbvG08 displayed
106 the expected ubiquitin-like fold consisting of a five-strand β -sheet (β 1-5) buttressed against a
107 single α -helix (α 1) and a short 3_{10} helix. However, it harbored one notable difference from the
108 canonical Ub fold: the register of strand β 5 was shifted 4 positions from its expected position,

109 resulting in an increase in the length of the loop preceding strand β 5 by 4 residues and a
110 shortening of the C-terminal tail of β 5 by 4 residues (Supplementary Fig. 1bc).

111 Complex formation was achieved by association of the β -sheet surface of UbvG08
112 centred on β 1, β 2 and β 5, with the ligand-binding surface of the 53BP1 Tudor domain (Fig. 2a).
113 This surface on the Ubv is adjacent to but distinct from the I44-centred hydrophobic patch that
114 mediates the majority of Ub-protein interactions¹⁵. The contact surfaces were extensive (buried
115 surface area=755.4 Å²), and comprised of a mixture of hydrophobic and hydrophilic residues
116 (Fig. 2b). Notable interactions include: 1) a hydrophobic cluster involving Tudor domain
117 residues Y1500, F1553 and I1587 and UbvG08 residues L2, F4 and L70; 2) a network of salt and
118 hydrogen-bonding interactions linking Tudor domain residues Y1502 and D1521 and UbvG08
119 residues T12 and K6; 3) a salt bridge between the Tudor domain residue E1551 and UbvG08
120 residue R72; 4) another salt bridge between Tudor domain residue E1575 and UbvG08 residue
121 K66; 5) a hydrophobic interaction between Tudor domain residue Y1552 that packs against
122 UbvG08 residues F45, P69 and L67 (Fig. 2c).

123 The high-affinity binding between UbvG08 and the Tudor domain of 53BP1 can be
124 rationalized as follows. Whereas the sequence of UbvG08 differs from wild type ubiquitin by 7
125 residues, only 4 substitutions are well positioned on the contact surface to allow direct
126 interaction of their side chains with 53BP1. Specifically, L70 (Val in Ub) forms favourable
127 hydrophobic contacts with 53BP1 F1553 and L1547; L2 (Gln in Ub) forms favourable
128 hydrophobic contacts with 53BP1 Y1500; and P69 (Leu in Ub) forms favourable hydrophobic
129 contact with 53BP1 Y1552 (Fig. 2c). Additionally K66 (Thr in Ub) is well positioned to form an
130 electrostatic interaction with 53BP1 E1575 (Fig. 2c).

131 Other substitutions in UbvG08 may contribute to enhanced binding indirectly by

132 stabilizing a shift in the register of strand $\beta 5$. The L62 mutation (Gln in Ub) appears most
133 important, as it resides at the initiating position of the normally tight loop preceding $\beta 5$ in Ub
134 (Supplementary Fig. 1d). The L62 substitution causes a reorientation of the side chain from a
135 solvent-exposed orientation (in Ub) to a buried position (in UbvG08) in the hydrophobic core,
136 which would be disruptive to tight turn formation. Additionally, the substituted side chains of
137 D64 (Glu in Ub) and K66 (Thr in Ub) occupy new positions in the enlarged solvent-exposed
138 loop preceding $\beta 5$, whereas in the absence of a register shift, they would occupy positions in
139 strand $\beta 3$ directly facing the Tudor domain where they might otherwise contribute suboptimal
140 interactions with 53BP1 (Supplementary Fig. 1e). The register difference in strand $\beta 5$ adds an
141 additional layer of complexity due to the non-substituted R72 side-chain displaced by 17 Å from
142 its expected position in Ub, allowing it to form a near ideal salt interaction with E1551 in the
143 Tudor domain (Fig. 2c). Finally, based on its position remote from both the contact surface with
144 53BP1 and strand $\beta 3$ of the UbvG08, we predict that S49 (Gln in Ub) does not contribute
145 materially to the binding affinity for 53BP1 (Fig. 2c).

146 To validate the functional significance of features observed in the crystal complex, we
147 interrogated the respective binding surfaces with site-directed mutagenesis. We first assessed the
148 impact of individually reverting each of the 7 substitutions in UbvG08 to their Ub counterparts.
149 The L2Q, L62Q, D64E, P69L and L70V reversions all reduced UbvG08 binding to 53BP1 in
150 pulldown assays, with the P69L and L70V mutations having the strongest effect (Fig. 2d).
151 Indeed, simultaneous reversions of P69 and L70 to their Ub counterparts (Ubv08-DM)
152 completely abolished UbvG08 binding to the 53BP1 Tudor domain, as measured by ITC (Fig.
153 1g). In a converse set of experiments, we found that the simultaneous mutation of the equivalent
154 residues in Ub into their UbvG08 counterparts were sufficient to convert Ub into a robust

155 53BP1-binding protein, as measured in pulldown assays (Fig. 2e). We also assessed the
156 importance of the non-substituted (i.e. same as Ub) residues in UbvG08 (Fig. 2f) as well as the
157 residues on the 53BP1 Tudor domain predicted by our model to be engaged in key interactions
158 (Supplementary Fig. 2ab). These analyses strongly validated the structural model of the
159 UbvG08-53BP1 interaction.

160 We next tested whether intracellular expression of UbvG08 could inhibit 53BP1 in cells.
161 We prepared Flag-tagged versions of UbvG08 and the DM mutant. The C-terminal di-glycine
162 motif was removed to preclude its incorporation in the active ubiquitin pool and we also
163 incorporated a I44A mutation, which disables the majority of ubiquitin-dependent interactions¹⁵
164 but does not impact the interaction of UbvG08 with 53BP1 (Fig. 2d). This version of Ubv-G08 is
165 referred to hereafter as *inhibitor of 53BP1* or i53 for reasons that will become apparent below.

166 When U-2-OS (U2OS) cells transfected with vectors expressing i53 or its DM mutant
167 were irradiated with a 10 Gy dose of X-rays, we observed that i53 but not the 53BP1-binding
168 defective DM mutant strongly suppressed 53BP1 recruitment to DSB sites, as monitored by
169 ionizing radiation focus formation (Fig. 3a,b). The inhibition of focus formation was specific to
170 53BP1, as i53 did not impact γ -H2AX and BRCA1 focus formation (Fig. 3a and Supplementary
171 Fig. 3a). Transfection of i53 also induced BRCA1 accumulation at DSB sites in G1 cells¹¹ to a
172 similar extent as that caused by loss of 53BP1^{11, 16}, providing a first clue that i53 not only inhibits
173 53BP1 recruitment to damaged chromatin but also acts as an inhibitor of 53BP1 function (Fig. 3c
174 and Supplementary Fig. 3b). i53, but not its DM mutant efficiently retrieved 53BP1 in co-
175 immunoprecipitation experiments (Fig. 3d) suggesting that the inhibition of 53BP1 recruitment
176 to DSB sites occurs through binding to 53BP1 and occlusion of the Tudor domain ligand binding
177 site.

178 Although UbvG08, the parent molecule of i53, shows a high degree of selectivity towards
179 53BP1 in ELISA assays (Fig. 1b), we sought to determine the repertoire of cellular proteins
180 bound by i53. We generated 293T Flp-In/T-Rex cell lines that expressed Flag-tagged i53 or i53-
181 DM under the control of a tetracycline-inducible promoter as previously described¹⁷. Nine IP-
182 MS experiments were analyzed (3 biological replicate IPs each for control, i53- and i53-DM
183 expressing cell lines) and the interacting proteins were identified by MASCOT. The only protein
184 found to interact with i53 in two or more experiments was 53BP1 (Table S2). We conclude that
185 i53 is a highly selective binder of 53BP1 in cells.

186 Loss of 53BP1 results in increased HDR levels¹⁸, making inhibitors of 53BP1 potential
187 tools to manipulate DSB repair pathways during genome engineering reactions. However, the
188 depletion of 53BP1 by siRNA, while near complete as determined by immunoblotting
189 (Supplementary Fig. 4a the a label is missing in the figure), is often insufficient to induce HDR
190 in the well-characterized direct-repeat (DR)-GFP assay¹⁹ (Fig. 3e,f). We therefore tested whether
191 i53 impacted gene conversion frequency and observed that i53 led to a 2.4-fold (+/-0.25)
192 increase in gene conversion when compared to the empty vector control, whereas the i53-DM
193 mutant had virtually no impact on gene conversion (1.25-fold +/-0.17; Fig. 3g and
194 Supplementary Fig. 4b). As a point of comparison, we compared i53 to SCR7, the reported
195 inhibitor of the NHEJ factor DNA ligase IV²⁰, which has been shown in some systems to
196 increase homology-dependent repair^{21, 22}. We also tested its related pyrazine analog, which has
197 been proposed to be the active SCR7 analog
198 (<https://www.tocris.com/dispprod.php?ItemId=432017#.VvUhq-t-rSRs>). Under our experimental
199 conditions, i53 was a more potent inducer of gene conversion, compared to both SCR7 and to
200 SCR7 pyrazine, which had minimal impact in this assay (Fig. 3h and Supplementary Fig. 4c).

201 As an orthogonal approach, we next tested whether i53 expression increased the
202 efficiency of gene targeting stimulated by CRISPR/Cas9. We took advantage of recently
203 described gene-targeting assays that involve the introduction of the coding sequences of
204 fluorescent proteins such as mClover, mAG or mCherry in frame with the coding regions of
205 Lamin A (*LMNA*)^{16, 23} or histone H2B (*HIST1H2BK*)²⁴. Precise HDR results in the expression of
206 fluorescent protein fusions that can be detected by flow cytometry for quantitation. We first
207 assessed gene targeting at the *LMNA* locus in U2OS cells, which is not responsive to SCR7
208 treatment²³, suggesting that end-joining may not provide a strong barrier to HR at this locus.
209 Similarly, inhibition of DNA-PK, a core NHEJ factor, with NU7441 only resulted in a modest
210 increase in gene targeting in this assay (Fig. 4a). However, we observed that i53, but not the DM
211 mutant, increased gene-targeting nearly two-fold (from 4.8% +/- 0.5% for the empty vector
212 control to 8.6% +/- 0.6% for the i53 condition). The gene-targeting efficiency in i53-expressing
213 cells approached that of 53BP1-null cells (*53BP1*Δ*KO*)¹⁶, suggesting that the inhibition of
214 53BP1 was near complete. Introduction of i53 in *53BP1*-ΔΔ cells did not result in a further
215 increase in gene targeting, demonstrating that the effect of i53 on HR is via inhibition of 53BP1.
216 Combining DNA-PK inhibition and i53 only led to a very modest increase in gene targeting,
217 perhaps in line with the dual function of 53BP1 in promoting NHEJ and inhibiting end-
218 joining??????? HDR.

219 The experiments above were undertaken with i53 delivered using plasmid transfection.
220 Since adeno-associated virus (AAV)-mediated gene delivery is a method of choice for the
221 delivery of gene editing components in vivo, we tested whether AAV-mediated delivery of i53
222 could also stimulate HDR. We found that AAV-delivered i53, but not i53-DM, robustly
223 stimulated gene conversion in U2OS cells using the DR-GFP assays (Supplementary Fig. 4d,e),

224 indicating that i53 can be delivered by AAV into a wide variety of cell types and tissues. We
225 next used AAV-mediated i53 delivery to assess its ability to stimulate homology-driven insertion
226 of the coding sequence for the fluorescent protein mAG at the 3' end of the *HIST1H2BK* open
227 reading frame. In those experiments, Cas9-sgRNA ribonucleoprotein (RNP) complexes and
228 dsDNA plasmid donors were nucleofected into 293T or K562 cells. The i53 molecule stimulated
229 gene targeting at the *HIST1H2BK* locus in both 293T and K562 cells, with the extent of
230 stimulation being more pronounced in K562 cells (Supplementary Fig. 5a,b). The simultaneous
231 nucleofection of donors inserting either mAG or mCherry at the *HIST1H2BK* locus next allowed
232 us to estimate whether i53 could stimulate bi-allelic modification of this locus simply by
233 monitoring cells that simultaneously express both fluorescent proteins²⁴. We observed that
234 indeed, i53 stimulated both mono- and bi-allelic gene targeting at the *HIST1H2BK* locus in K562
235 cells (Fig 4b and Supplementary Fig. 5c).

236 In parallel, we also assessed if AAV-delivered i53 could stimulate HDR in mouse cells,
237 since the 53BP1 Tudor domain is highly homologous in vertebrates. We employed a gene-
238 targeting assay conceptually similar to those described above where the incorporation of a *t2A-*
239 *ZsGreen* cassette at the *Hsp90ab1* locus is monitored by flow cytometry. We found that i53
240 stimulated gene-targeting in mouse embryo fibroblasts (Fig 4c and Supplementary Fig. 6)
241 indicating that AAV-mediated i53 stimulates HDR in both human and mouse cells.

242 In addition to AAV-mediated delivery, delivery of mRNA is another means for
243 introducing gene-editing components in primary cells^{25, 26}. We therefore tested whether
244 electroporation of an i53-coding mRNA stimulated zinc finger nuclease (ZFN)-mediated gene
245 targeting at the *CCR5* locus in K562 using a dsDNA donor used previously^{26, 27}. We found that
246 mRNA delivery of i53 robustly increased gene targeting stimulated by a ZFN (Fig 4d) and

247 resulted in a corresponding decrease of indels at the site of cleavage, as detected by the CEL1
248 nuclease ([Supplementary Fig. 7a](#)). These results indicate that i53-mediated stimulation of HDR is
249 independent of the nuclease or delivery method employed and they suggest that i53 acts by
250 skewing DSB repair pathway choice towards HDR.

251 Canonical, RAD51-dependent HDR is the dominant pathway for gene conversion
252 with large dsDNA donors²⁸. In contrast, HDR using single-stranded oligonucleotide (ssODN)
253 donors involves a poorly understood RAD51-independent annealing-type mechanism²⁹. Since
254 ssODN-mediated HDR is an important gene modification method and since the impact of 53BP1
255 inhibition on these reactions could not be predicted from the experiments above, we examined
256 the impact of i53 on the ssODN-mediated conversion of GFP to BFP in 293T and MCF10a cells
257 following a Cas9-induced DSB, as previously described³⁰ ([Fig 4e](#) and [Supplementary Fig. 7b,c](#)).
258 We observed, with both optimal and suboptimal ssODN donors, that i53 stimulated HDR in this
259 assay by approximately 30%-40%, depending on the donor and cell line used. We next modified
260 two endogenous loci, *CXCR4* and *CCR5*, to introduce new restriction endonuclease sites by
261 ssODN-mediated HDR in both 293T and K562 cells. We observed that i53 stimulated HDR with
262 ssODN donors up to 3.3 (+/- 0.8) fold in 293T cells ([Fig 4f](#) and [Supplementary Fig. 7d,e](#)), again
263 with a concomitant decrease in indel formation at the same loci ([Supplementary Fig. 7f](#)). These
264 data indicate that i53 stimulates HDR with ssODN donors at multiple loci and cell types.
265 Interestingly, these data also suggested that DNA end resection plays an important role in
266 ssODN-mediated HDR. In support of this idea, depletion of CtIP, a key end-resection factor⁴,
267 reduced HDR by ssODN in 293T cells by nearly 50% in the GFP-to-BFP conversion assay ([Fig](#)
268 [4g \(h???\)](#) and [Supplementary Fig. 8a,b](#) are the two plots in S8a with siCtIP). DNA end resection
269 inhibits NHEJ but can activate alternative end-joining pathways in addition to activating HR³¹.

270 Resection can reveal regions of microhomology that may be rejoined in a process termed
271 microhomology-mediated end joining (MMEJ)³¹. The impact of 53BP1 on this repair process is
272 unclear due to conflicting results^{32, 33}. To assess whether 53BP1 inhibition by i53 increases
273 MMEJ, we employed the EJ2-GFP reporter assay^{34, 35}. We found that i53 expression increased
274 MMEJ (1.4 +/- 0.2 fold over the empty vector; [Supplementary Fig. 8c,d](#)) but since the expression
275 of the DM mutant also increased MMEJ to a similar extent (1.3 +/- 0.1 fold), it is unlikely that
276 the increase in MMEJ observed following i53 expression was due to 53BP1 inhibition.

277 In summary, we report the development of a genetically encoded inhibitor of 53BP1 that
278 robustly stimulates canonical and ssODN-mediated homology-directed repair of DSBs. In
279 addition to gene targeting applications, i53 could be useful in additional gene editing reactions
280 where the engagement of the HR pathway is desired. As an example, since the DR-GFP assay
281 can be viewed as an interparalog gene conversion reaction, it is tempting to predict that i53 will
282 stimulate the correction of the mutated *HBB* hemoglobin gene by conversion with its paralog
283 *HBD* for the treatment of sickle cell anemia. Other applications could include gene drives³⁶ (i.e.
284 stimulated interhomolog recombination). Importantly, i53 expression does not impact
285 spontaneous or DNA damage-stimulated sister chromatid exchanges (SCEs), a potential threat to
286 genome stability that occurs as a consequence of crossover reactions ([Supplementary Fig. 8e-h](#)).

287 The 53BP1 Tudor domain is highly conserved across a wide range of vertebrate species
288 including agriculturally important animals such as pigs and cows; and we have shown that i53
289 can also stimulate HDR in mouse cells. Thus we expect that i53 could be used to stimulate HR in
290 those species as well.

291 The observation that i53 stimulates HDR by ssODNs led us to ascertain that CtIP, a key
292 resection factor, also promotes this type of gene editing reaction. This is in line with the

293 annealing-driven strand synthesis (ADSS) model of HDR by ssODNs²⁹, which also suggests that
294 end resection creates annealing targets for oligonucleotides. Interestingly, CtIP depletion only
295 led to a ~50% reduction in HDR by ssODN raising the possibility that ADSS is not the only
296 HDR pathway operating at DSBs or that Cas9-mediated cleavage might engage CtIP-
297 independent resection. Deciphering how these pathways operate will assuredly provide new
298 opportunities for intervention and synergy with 53BP1 inhibition.

299 The versatility of the ubiquitin scaffold onto which i53 is built, along with the
300 determination of the molecular basis of the i53-53BP1 interaction should enable us to improve
301 53BP1 inhibition either through protein engineering or through affinity maturation of the
302 UbvG08 via additional rounds of mutagenesis and phage display selections. Nevertheless, we
303 generally observe a good correlation between suppression of 53BP1 recruitment to DSB sites, as
304 measured by ionizing-radiation focus formation, and stimulation of HDR. Monitoring DSB-
305 induced 53BP1 focus formation can therefore be used as a means to assess whether the
306 expression levels of i53 are high enough to have a desired effect in any cell type.

307 Finally, DNA ligase IV inhibition by SCR7²⁰ was recently reported to stimulate
308 homology-based genome editing^{21, 22}. However, under our experimental conditions, we found i53
309 to be a more robust activator of HR than SCR7 or the DNA-PK inhibitor NU7441. We note that
310 there might be safety concerns in the use of DNA ligase IV inhibitors, as DNA ligase IV
311 deficiency is associated with stem cell depletion and genome instability, especially in the
312 hematopoietic stem cell compartment^{37, 38}. We therefore propose that 53BP1 inhibition could be
313 a propitious alternative for boosting HR rates, which can also be used in combination with other
314 methods, such as the recently described marker-free co-selection strategy based on the
315 modification of the *ATP1A1* gene²⁴.

316

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330

331 **Author contributions**

332 MDC generated the mutations for the analysis by pulldown and carried out most of the pulldown
333 experiments, generated the protein crystals, conducted the ITC experiments, and carried out
334 some of the initial assays demonstrating efficiency of i53. NM carried out the DR- and EJ2-GFP
335 assays, all assays with AAV-i53 in human cells along with all ssODN assays and the
336 determination of 53BP1 foci in G1 cells. LW refined and analyzed the crystal structure and
337 prepared the figures describing the structure. AFT produced the GST-53BP1 protein for Ubv
338 selection and the GST-fusion Ubv proteins for the initial pulldown assays she carried out. YCJ

339 supervised the crystallization and collected the diffraction data. AO carried out the *LMNA* gene
340 targeting assays with the help of TN. WZ carried out the Ubv selections with AV and AE.. SMN
341 carried out the PARP inhibitor assays using cells generated by MZ. MDW helped with
342 biochemical experiments. PAM-G designed and performed the experiment in mouse cells. MM
343 did the IP-MS and helped MDC, AFT and AO. SSS supervised WZ, AV and AE. FS supervised
344 LW and YCJ. DD conceived and supervised the project and wrote the manuscript with LW,
345 MDC and FS, with input from the other authors.

346
347 Correspondence and requests should be addressed to durocher@lunenfeld.ca
348

349 **METHODS**

350

351 **Cell culture and treatments**

352 U-2-OS (U2OS) and 293T cells were obtained from ATCC. 293T and HEK293 Flp-In/T-REx
353 cells (Invitrogen) were propagated in DMEM medium supplemented with 10% fetal bovine
354 serum (FBS, Gibco) and 2 mM L-alanyl-L-glutamine, and were maintained in a 37 °C and 5%
355 CO₂ atmosphere. U2OS cells were grown in McCoy's medium supplemented with 10% FBS.
356 U2OS DR-GFP and EJ2-GFP cells were a gift of Jeremy Stark. *53BP1Δ* U2OS and U2OS cell
357 lines stably expressing CtIP-T847E were previously described¹⁶. MEFs were cultured in
358 Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum
359 (FBS) (Gibco), 2 mM L-glutamine (Sigma), 100 U/ml penicillin (Sigma), 0.1 μg/ml
360 streptomycin (Sigma), 0.1 mM non-essential amino acids (Invitrogen), and 1 mM sodium
361 pyruvate (Sigma).

362 RPE1 hTERT cells were obtained from ATCC and maintained in DMEM + 10% FCS. A
363 Flag-Cas9-2A-Blast expression cassette was integrated as described before³⁹. Upon single clone
364 selection, cells were maintained in the presence of 2 µg/mL blasticidin. The *TP53* gene was
365 knocked-out using transient transfection of the LentiGuide plasmid with Lipofectamine. 24 h
366 post-transfection, cells were selected for 24 h with 15 µg/mL puromycin, followed by a 5-day
367 recovery and 48 h selection with 10 µM of the MDM2 inhibitor Nutlin-3 (Cayman Chemical)
368 after which single clones were isolated and verified for loss of p53 protein. Furthermore,
369 CRISPR-generated indel mutations in the *TP53* gene were verified by PCR amplification of the
370 region surrounding the sgRNA target sequence, cloning of products into the pCR2.1 TOPO
371 vector (TOPO TA Cloning kit, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and Sanger sequencing of individual
372 bacterial clones (forward PCR-primer: GCATTGAAGTCTCATGGAAGC, reverse PCR-primer:
373 TCACTGCCATGGAGGAGC). *53BP1* and/or *BRCA1* gene knockouts were generated by
374 electroporation of the respective LentiGuide vectors (Lonza Amaxa II Nucleofector, program T-
375 023, 5 µg plasmid per 700,000 cells). 24 h post transfection, cells were selected for 24 hr with 15
376 µg/mL puromycin, followed by single clone isolation. The double *53BP1/BRCA1*Δ cell line was
377 created by deleting *BRCA1* from the *53BP1* single knock-out cell line. Gene mutations were
378 further confirmed by PCR amplification and sequencing as described above for *TP53* (*53BP1*
379 forward PCR-primer: CCAGCACCAACAAGAGC, *53BP1* reverse PCR-primer:
380 GGATGCCTGGTACTGTTTGG, *BRCA1* forward PCR-primer:
381 TCTCAAAGTATTTTCATTTTCTTGGTGCC, *BRCA1* reverse PCR-primer:
382 TGAGCAAGGATCATAAAATGTTGG). Retrovirus of GFP (IRES-GFP), i53-IRES-GFP and
383 DM-IRES-GFP was generated in 293T cells by transient transfection of the pMX-IRES-GFP
384 vector together with the packaging vectors VSVG and Gag-Pol using LT1 transfection reagent

385 (Mirus). Supernatants containing retrovirus were collected and filtered through 0.45 μ m filters.
386 RPE1 cells were transduced in two hits (24 h apart) to an MOI of \approx 0.8 in the presence of 8
387 μ g/mL polybrene and sorted for GFP 72 h after the second hit. All cells were >97% positive for
388 GFP throughout the experiments, as based on FACS analysis. All cell lines tested negative for
389 mycoplasma contamination and the identity of cell lines confirmed by STR analysis.

390

391 **Plasmids**

392 The phagemid (DDp2235) from the UbvG08 phage was obtained from the ubiquitin variant
393 library described in ⁶; see below for details. The UbvG08 open reading frame (ORF) lacking the
394 C-terminal di-Gly residues was cloned into a pDONR vector using a product from PCR
395 amplification of the phagemid template and Gateway recombination, yielding plasmid DDp2251
396 (UbvG08 Δ GG). The pETM-30-2-GST-UbvG08 (DDp2186) and pETM30-2-GST-ubiquitin
397 (DDp2192) were cloned following PCR amplification from the UbvG08 Δ GG or Ub Δ GG ORFs,
398 respectively. The constructs encoding His6-GST-TEV and MBP fusions of 53BP1 Tudor-UDR
399 (residues 1484-1631) and Tudor (residues 1484-1603) domains were described previously in¹³.
400 The I44A mutation was introduced into DDp2186, which was then used as a template for
401 amplification of the modified Ubv by PCR. The PCR product was cloned into the BamHI and
402 NotI sites of a pcDNA3-Flag plasmid to yield pcDNA3-Flag-i53 (DDp2534). The BamHI-NotI
403 fragment of DDp2534 was subsequently cloned into a pcDNA5-Flag-FRT/TO Flag vector to
404 yield plasmid DDp2535. All other plasmids were generated by site-directed mutagenesis carried
405 out by Quikchange (Agilent). The lentiviral vector coding for a siRNA-resistant Flag-tagged
406 CtIP T847E construct was previously described¹⁶. The plasmids used for the *LMNA* assay were
407 gifts of G. Dellaire²³.

408 Single guide (sg)RNAs targeting *TP53* (CAGAATGCAAGAAGCCCAGA), *BRC1*
409 (AAGGGTAGCTGTTAGAAGGC) and *53BP1* (TCCAATCCTGAACAAACAGC) were cloned
410 into lentiGuide-Puro (Addgene: #52963) as described⁴⁰. The i53 and DM lentiviral expression
411 vectors were prepared by PCR amplification that also introduced sequences coding for an N-
412 terminal HA-tag and flanking PacI and NotI restriction sites. The PCR products were cloned in
413 the PacI and NotI sites of pMX-IRES-GFP (a gift from A. Nussenzweig, National Institutes of
414 Health). The Lenti-Cas9-2A-Blast construct was a gift from J. Moffat (University of Toronto).
415 All constructs were sequence-verified.

416 To prepare AAV-i53 and i53-DM vectors, the region comprising Flag-i53 (or i53-DM)
417 was PCR-amplified from pcDNA3-i53 and pcDNA3-i53-DM with the addition of a 5' ClaI site
418 and 3' HindIII site. The GFP insert was excised from pAAV-GFP (Cell Biolabs) and replaced
419 with the ClaI- and HindIII-flanked Flag-UbV PCR products to produce pAAV-Flag-i53-DM and
420 pAAV-Flag-i53, which were verified by diagnostic digests and sequencing.

421 To facilitate monitoring of mono- versus bi-allelic editing, the mAG coding sequence in
422 the *HISTH2BK*-mAG donor plasmid (gift of Y. Doyon) was exchanged for mCherry. The
423 mCherry gene was PCR amplified from a pCDNA5-FRT/TO-mCherry plasmid, flanked by a 5'
424 KpnI site, and a 3' BsrGI site. The reverse primer simultaneously served to silently mutate a
425 naturally occurring BsrGI site at the 3' end of the mCherry sequence. The PCR product and
426 *HISTH2BK*-mAG1 plasmid were digested with KpnI and BsrGI, and gel-purified. The PCR
427 fragment was then ligated into the *HISTH2BK* donor vector, and clones were screened by
428 diagnostic digest, and confirmed by sequencing.

429 The vectors pcDNA3-Flag-i53 (#74939), pcDNA3-Flag-i53-DM (#74940), pAAV-Flag-
430 i53 (#92170) and pAAV-Flag-i53-DM (#92171) have been deposited at Addgene.

431

432 **Selection of and purification of the 53BP1-binding ubiquitin variants**

433 The phage-displayed Ubv library used in this study was re-amplified from Library 2 as
434 previously described⁶. Protein immobilization and subsequent phage selections were performed
435 according to established protocols⁴¹. Briefly, purified 53BP1 protein fragments were coated on
436 96-well MaxiSorp plates (Thermo Scientific 12565135) by adding 100 μ L of 1 μ M proteins and
437 incubating overnight at 4 °C. Afterwards, five rounds of selection using the phage-displayed Ubv
438 library were performed against immobilized proteins. A total of 96 phage clones obtained from
439 the fourth and the fifth round of binding selections (48 from each round) were subjected to clonal
440 ELISA to identify individual phages that bound to 53BP1. The sequences of phage-displayed
441 Ubvs were derived by sequencing of the phagemid DNA⁴¹. For phage ELISA, proteins in study
442 (53BP1 and/or control proteins) were immobilized on 384-well MaxiSorp plates (Thermo
443 Scientific 12665347) by adding 30 μ L of 1 μ M proteins for overnight incubation at 4 °C before
444 adding amplified phages (1:3 dilution in PBS + 1% BSA + 0.05% Tween) and incubated
445 overnight. Binding of phage was detected using anti-M13-HRP antibody (GE Healthcare
446 27942101).

447

448 **Pulldowns**

449 MBP and GST pulldowns were done essentially as described in ref¹³ with the modifications
450 described below. We used the following buffer for the binding reactions: 50 mM Tris-Cl pH 7.5,
451 50 mM NaCl, 0.01% NP40 and 1% BSA. We also used 2.5 μ g of the MBP- and GST-fusion
452 proteins as baits. For peptide competition pulldowns 2.5 μ g MBP-53BP1-Tudor was coupled to
453 amylose resin (New England Biolabs) and 0.75 μ g GST-UbvG08 was added simultaneously to a

454 biotin-labeled peptide derived from histone H4K20me2 (Biotin-Mini-PEG-
455 YGKGGAKRHRKme2VLRD; BioBasic Canada Inc.) for 2 h at 4°C. Peptide pulldowns were
456 washed in binding buffer, eluted with SDS-PAGE sample buffer, and analyzed by
457 immunoblotting. For all pulldowns, 1-2% of the total amount of the input proteins was separated
458 by SDS-PAGE and probed for immunoblotting.

459

460 **Protein expression, crystallization and structure determination**

461 The 53BP1 Tudor domain (residues 1784-1603) and UbvG08 were individually expressed and
462 purified from bacteria as GST-tagged fusion proteins. In brief, GST-tagged fusion proteins were
463 purified from bacterial lysates on to glutathione-Sepharose (GE Healthcare), washed, and then
464 eluted by TEV protease digestion to GST moieties, followed by purification by size exclusion
465 chromatography (SEC). The 53BP1 Tudor-UbvG08 complex was formed by mixing purified
466 proteins at equimolar concentration, incubating overnight at 4 °C, and purifying the complex by
467 SEC in 10 mM Tris-Cl pH 7.5, 150 mM NaCl and 1 mM DTT column buffer. Crystals of the
468 complex were grown at 20 °C using the hanging drop vapor diffusion method by mixing equal
469 volumes (1 µL) of complex at 28.5 mg/ml with crystallization buffer consisting of 0.1 M MES
470 pH 6.0, 0.2 M trimethylamine N-oxide and 25% (w/v) PEG MME 2000. Crystals were cryo-
471 protected by a quick soak in crystallization buffer supplemented with 20% glycerol, prior to flash
472 freezing. A single crystal dataset was collected at -180 °C on a home-source consisting of a
473 Rigaku MicroMax-007 HF rotating anode generator, coupled to a R-axis 4++ detector (Rigaku)
474 and VariMax multilayer optics. Data processing was performed using the XDS software suite.
475 The structure of a single 53BP1 Tudor-UbvG08 complex in the asymmetric unit was solved by
476 molecular replacement using the apo Tudor domain (PDB 2IG0) and ubiquitin (PDB 3NHE

477 chain B) as search models in Phaser (Phenix suite). Structure refinement was performed using
478 Refine (Phenix suite). See [Table S1](#) for data collection and refinement statistics.

479

480 **Immunoprecipitation**

481 293T cells were transfected with 10 µg of pcDNA3-Flag-i53-derived plasmids using
482 polyethylenimine (PEI). 48 h post-transfection, cells were lysed in 1 mL high salt lysis buffer (50
483 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 300 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% (v/v) Triton X-100, and 1X protease
484 inhibitors (Complete, EDTA-free, Roche)) and cell lysates were clarified by centrifugation at 4
485 °C. 100 µL was removed as the input sample. The remaining lysate was incubated with ~15 µL
486 anti-Flag (M2) affinity gel (Sigma) for 2 h at 4 °C. The immunoprecipitates were then washed
487 twice with high salt lysis buffer, once with 50 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 0.1 mM EDTA and eluted
488 in 25 µL 2X Laemmli sample buffer for analysis by immunoblotting.

489

490 **Antibodies**

491 We employed the following antibodies: rabbit anti-53BP1 (A300-273A, Bethyl), mouse anti-γ-
492 H2AX (clone JBW301, Millipore), mouse anti-53BP1 (#612523, BD Biosciences), rabbit anti-
493 GST (sc-459, Santa Cruz), a mouse anti-HA (F-7, sc-7392, SantaCruz or clone 12CA5, gift from
494 M. Tyers, University of Montréal), mouse anti-MBP (E8032S, NEB), mouse anti-Flag (clone
495 M2, Sigma), rabbit anti-Flag (#2368, Cell Signaling), mouse anti-tubulin (clone DM1A,
496 Calbiochem), mouse anti-p53 (sc-126, Santa Cruz), rabbit anti-ubiquitin (Z0458, DAKO), rabbit
497 anti-BRCA1 (#07-434, Millipore or home-made antibody¹¹). Goat anti-GFP (gift from L.
498 Pelletier, Lunenfeld-Tanenbaum Research Institute), HRP-conjugated AffiniPure goat anti-rabbit
499 IgG (Jackson ImmunoResearch), HRP-linked sheep anti-mouse IgG (NA931, GE Healthcare).

500 Alexa Fluor 488 goat anti-mouse and anti-rabbit IgG, Alexa Fluor 555 goat anti-mouse and anti-
501 rabbit (MolecularProbes).

502

503 **RNA interference**

504 All siRNAs employed in this study were single duplex siRNAs purchased from ThermoFisher.

505 RNA interference (RNAi) transfections were performed using Lipofectamine RNAiMax

506 (Invitrogen) in a forward transfection mode. The individual siRNA duplexes used were *BRCA1*

507 (D-003461-05), *CtIP/RBBP8* (M-001376-00), *53BP1/T53BP1* (D-003549-01), *KEAP1* (D-

508 12453-02) or *53BP1/T53BP1* (D-003548-01), non-targeting control siRNA (D-001210-02).

509 Except when stated otherwise, siRNAs were transfected 48 h before cell processing.

510

511 **Inhibitors and fine chemicals**

512 The following drugs and chemicals were used: DNA-PKcs inhibitor (NU7441; Genetex) at

513 10 μ M, lovastatin (S2061; Selleck Chemicals) at 40 μ M, doxycycline (#8634-1; Clontech),

514 SCR7 (M60082-2; Xcessbio) at 1 μ M. Olaparib was purchased from Selleck Chemicals.

515

516 **AAV production.**

517 The viral supernatant of AAV293 cells (Agilent Technologies) was collected and used for

518 infections 48 h after co-transfection with 3.5 μ g each of expression plasmid, pDJ and pHelper

519 (Cell BioLabs). For MEFs, the viral supernatant was first concentrated in Amicon Ultra-15

520 Centrifugal Filter Unit with Ultracel-100 membrane.

521

522 **Preparation of RNPs**

523 Purified SpCas9 was diluted to a concentration of 3.2 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$ in Cas9 buffer (20 mM HEPES (pH
524 7.5), 150 mM KCl, 1 mM MgCl_2 , 10% glycerol and 1 mM TCEP), and sgRNA was diluted to a
525 concentration of 0.8 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$ in Cas9 buffer. 5 μl of diluted Cas9 was slowly mixed into 5 μl of
526 diluted sgRNA, then incubated for 10-20 minutes at room temperature.

527

528 **Immunofluorescence microscopy**

529 Cells were grown on glass coverslips, fixed with 2% (w/v) paraformaldehyde in PBS for 20 min
530 at room temperature, permeabilized with 0.3% (v/v) Triton X-100 for 20 min at room
531 temperature and blocked with 5% BSA in PBS for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were then
532 incubated with the primary antibody diluted in PBS-BSA for 2 h at room temperature. Cells were
533 next washed with PBS and then incubated with secondary antibodies diluted in PBS-BSA
534 supplemented with 0.8 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of DAPI (Sigma) to stain DNA for 1 h at room temperature. The
535 coverslips were mounted onto glass slides with Prolong Gold mounting agent (Invitrogen).
536 Confocal images were taken using a Zeiss LSM780 laser-scanning microscope.

537

538 **Reporter-based DNA repair assays**

539 The direct repeat (DR)-GFP assay to measure the frequency of HR and the strand annealing EJ2-
540 GFP assay to measure the frequency of MMEJ were performed as previously described³⁴.
541 Briefly, U2OS DR-GFP or U2OS EJ2-GFP cells were transfected with 10 nM siRNA
542 (Dharmacon) using Lipofectamine RNAiMAX (Invitrogen). 24 h later, the cells were transfected
543 with the pCBASceI plasmid (Addgene #26477) and plasmids, using Lipofectamine 2000
544 (Invitrogen). 48 h post-plasmid transfection, the cells were trypsinized and the percentage of
545 GFP-expressing cells was analyzed using the BD FACSCalibur flow cytometer.

546 The Lamin A (*LMNA*) assay to measure the frequency of introduction of the coding
547 sequence for mClover at the 5' end of LMNA using the CRISPR/Cas9 was performed as
548 previously described¹⁶. Parental or *53BP1Δ* U2OS cell lines were transfected with the indicated
549 plasmids using Lipofectamine RNAiMAX (Invitrogen). 24 h later, the cells were electroporated
550 with 2.5 μg of sgRNA plasmids and 2.5 μg of donor template using a Nucleofector (Lonza;
551 protocol X-001). Under those condition, omission of the sgRNA gives negligible levels of
552 mClover-positive cells¹⁶. Parental or *53BP1Δ* U2OS cells stably expressing CtIP-T847E mutant
553 were transfected with an siRNA against KEAP1 and the indicated plasmids and processed as
554 previously described¹⁶.

555 A FACS-based gene targeting assay was developed to monitor the targeting efficiency of
556 a Zsgreen reporter at the 3' end of Hsp90 locus. A homology repair template plasmid was
557 generated with the coding sequence of Zsgreen and homology arms (600 base pairs) that
558 correspond to sequence flanking the Hsp90 STOP codon. MEFs transduced with AAV i53 and
559 control cells expressing DM were co-transfected with a repair template plasmid and a plasmid
560 expressing Cas9 (pX330-U6-Chimeric_BB-CBh-hSpCas9) and a gRNA (5'-
561 CGATGAGGATGCCTCGCGCA-3'). One million cells were transfected with 200ng of
562 Cas9/gRNA plasmid and 800ng of template plasmid using Lipofectamine 3000 (Invitrogen)
563 according to the manufacturer's instruction. 16 hours later, cells were selected with puromycin (2
564 μg/ml) for 48 hours to enrich for cas9-expressing cells. To determine the percentage of Zsgreen
565 positive cells, cells were by analyzed by flow cytometry using a FACS Aria III cell sorter 8 days
566 post-transfection.

567 The *HISTH2BK* (H2B) targeting assay was adapted from ref²⁴ for use with Cas9 RNPs.
568 For the targeting assay, 1.25 μg of plasmid donor was used per nucleofection.

569

570 **BFP-to-GFP ssODN-based HDR assay**

571 293T cells were transduced at a low MOI (<0.3) with a lentivirus expressing BFP under the
572 control of an EF1 α promoter (Addgene #71825) and sorted by flow cytometry to produce a pure
573 population of BFP-expressing cells. One day post-AAV transduction, 2×10^5 cells were
574 resuspended in 20 μ l SF buffer (Lonza) and nucleofected with 10 μ l sgBFP RNP and 100 pmol
575 of ssODN donor, using program DS-150 on a Nucleofector 96-well Shuttle system (Lonza).
576 Cells were then transferred to a 12-well plate containing pre-warmed medium, and grown for 4
577 days. BFP and GFP fluorescence were measured by flow cytometry on a BD Fortessa, and the
578 results were analyzed using FlowJo v10 software.

579

580 **ssODN-based RFLP HDR assay**

581 The day post-AAV transduction 2×10^5 cells were resuspended in 20 μ l SF buffer (Lonza) and
582 nucleofected along with 10 μ l sgCCR5 or sgCXCR4 RNPs and 100 pmol of ssODN donor, using
583 program FF-120 (for K562 cells) or DS-150 (for 293T cells), respectively, on a Nucleofector 96-
584 well Shuttle system (Lonza). Cells were collected 3d post-nucleofection and their genomic DNA
585 isolated (Qiagen DNeasy kit). The *CCR5* and *CXCR4* loci were amplified by PCR from 400 ng
586 of genomic DNA using Pfx Platinum Polymerase (Invitrogen). 200 ng of purified PCR product
587 was digested overnight with PciI (NEB), then resolved on a 2% agarose gel and analyzed with
588 ImageQuant software.

589

590 **Mass spectrometry**

591 Following immunoprecipitation of Flag-tagged UbvG08 and UbvG08DM from HEK293 Flp-

592 In/T-REx cells, peptides were identified using LC-MS/MS. Proteins were digested in solution
593 with trypsin (Sigma, T7575-1KT) and dried to completeness. For LC-MS/MS analysis, peptides
594 were reconstituted in 5% formic acid and loaded onto a 12-15 cm fused silica column with pulled
595 tip packed in-house with 3.5 μ m Zorbax C18 (Agilent Technologies, CA, USA).
596 UbvG08 and UbvG08-DM were analyzed using an LTQ (Thermo Scientific) coupled to an
597 Agilent 1100 Series HPLC (Agilent Technologies). Peptides were eluted from the column using
598 a 90 min period cycle with a linear gradient from 0% to 40% ACN in 0.1% formic acid. Tandem
599 MS spectra were acquired in a data-dependent mode for the top 5 most abundant ions using
600 collision-induced dissociation. Acquired spectra were searched against the human Refseq_V53
601 database using Mascot (Matrix Science).

602

603 **Isothermal titration calorimetry**

604 Isothermal titration calorimetry was performed using a VP-ITC calorimeter (MicroCal).
605 Untagged 53BP1 Tudor and UbvG08 (or the DM mutant) were dialyzed into PBS and degassed.
606 100 μ M UbvG08 in the syringe was titrated into 10 μ M 53BP1 Tudor protein in the sample cell
607 using 30 consecutive 10 μ l injections at 25 °C. Resultant binding isotherms were processed with
608 Origin 5.0 software (Microcal). Curve fits were carried out using the one-set-of-sites model.

609

610 **ZFN editing reagents.** A ZFN pair targeting CCR5 has been previously described^{26, 42}. The ZFN
611 coding sequences were cloned into pVAX (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA), which was
612 linearized by restriction enzyme digestion to generate templates for mRNA synthesis, using the
613 mMESSAGE mMACHINE T7 ULTRA Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific), according to the

614 manufacturer's instructions. A CCR5 homologous sequence²⁶ containing an internal XhoI
615 restriction site, was used in its plasmid form as a homology donor.

616

617 **Analysis of gene disruption and editing by ZFNs.** K562 cells were obtained from the
618 American Type Culture Collection, and transfected by nucleofection as previously described²⁷,
619 using 16-well Nucleocuvette™ Strips in the 4D-Nucleofector™ System, and the SF Cell Line
620 4D-Nucleofector® X Kit S (Lonza, Cologne, Germany). Briefly, 2×10^5 cells were resuspended
621 in 20 μ L of SF solution, together with mRNA and/or plasmids, and nucleofected using the
622 recommended program for K562 cells. Two sequential nucleofections were performed, 24 hours
623 apart, to allow i53 or DM expression before delivery of ZFN mRNA and donor plasmids.
624 Cells were recounted and normalized prior to the second nucleofection. A total of 2.1, 4.2, or 6.3
625 pmol of i53/DM mRNAs, 1.8 pmol of each ZFN mRNA, and/or 0.3 pmol of donor plasmids
626 were used. K562 cell pellets were harvested 5 days after the last nucleofection and CCR5 gene
627 disruption rates determined using GeneArt® Genomic Cleavage Detection Kit (Thermo Fisher
628 Scientific) following the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, genomic DNA was extracted from
629 cell pellets and subject to PCR amplification using human CCR5-specific primers²⁶. The PCR
630 product was then denatured and reannealed in conditions allowing small DNA mismatch
631 reannealing, and a proprietary detection enzyme was added to cleave unmatched regions.
632 Digested PCR products were subject to electrophoresis on a 10% polyacrylamide gel, and gene
633 disruption rates determined based on densitometry analysis of cleaved and uncleaved products.
634 Gene editing rates were determined using an RFLP assay, as described^{26, 27}. Briefly, a pair of
635 CCR5 primers located outside the region of homology contained within the CCR5 donor

636 molecule were used for PCR amplification, followed by *Xho*I digestion, resolution on a 1%
 637 agarose gel, and analysis of products by densitometry.

638

639 **sgRNA targeting sequences**

Target	Guide sequence	Targeting Donor	Non-targeting donor
<i>BFP-1</i>	ATGGCG TGCAGT GCTTCA GC	GCCACCTACGGCAAGCTGACCCTGAA GTTTCATCTGCACCACCGGCAAGCTGC CCGTGCCCTGGCCACCCTCGTGACC ACCCTGACGTACGGCGTGACGTGCTT CAGCCGCTACCCCGACCACATGA	AGTGGCCAGAGTCCAGCTTGGGCCC ACGCAGGGGCTGGCCAGCAGCAA GCAGCACTCTGCCCTCGTGGGTTT TGGTTGCCACACATGTCATTGGAG GTGACATCGATGTCTCCCCATTGG CCT
<i>CCR5#</i>	TGACAT CAATTA TTATAC AT	ACAAAACCAAAGATGAACACCAGTG AGTAGAGCGGAGGCAGGAGGCGGGC TGCGATTTGCTTCACATTGATTTTTTG GCAGGGCT ^{cac} ATGTATAATAATTGAT GTCATAGATTGGACTTGACACTT	ATGGATTGGTCATCCTGGTCATGGG TTACCAGAAGAACTGAGAAGCAT GACGGACAAGTACAGGCTGCACCT GTCAGTGGCCGACATGTTCTTTGTC ATCACGCTTCCCTTCTGGGCAGTTG ATGC
<i>CXCR4</i> #	GAAGCG TGATGA CAAAGA GG	ATGGATTGGTCATCCTGGTCATGGGT TACCAGAAGAACTGAGAAGCATGA CGGACAAGTACAGGCTGCACCTGTCA GTGGCCGACATGTTCTTTGTCATCAC GCTTCCCTTCTGGGCAGTTGATGC	ACAAAACCAAAGATGAACACCAGT GAGTAGAGCGGAGGCAGGAGGCGG GCTGCGATTTGCTTCACATTGATTTT TTGGCAGGGCT ^{cac} ATGTATAATAAT TGATGTCATAGATTGGACTTGACAC TT
<i>HISTH</i> <i>2BK</i>	GGGGCT TTAAGA CGCTTA CT	Agudelo <i>et al.</i> ref ²⁴	N/A

640
 641
 642

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739 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

740

741 **Figure 1. Identification of 53BP1-binding ubiquitin variants.** **a**, Schematic representation of
742 53BP1, highlighting the focus-forming region (FFR), which is necessary and sufficient for the
743 recruitment of 53BP1 to DSB sites. **b**, Phage enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISAs) for
744 binding to the following immobilized proteins (color coded as indicated in the panel): USP5,
745 USP7, SMURF1, HACE, HOIP, HOIL, 53BP1 (Tudor-UDR region), NBD, SMURF2, CDC4,
746 OTUB1, FBW7, USP8, ITCH, USP21, USP14 and BSA. Bound phages were detected
747 spectrophotometrically (optical density at 450 nm), and background binding to neutravidin was
748 subtracted from the signal. **c**, Sequence alignments of the 53BP1-binding Ubvs. **d**, Pulldown
749 assays of the indicated GST-Ubv fusion with either MBP alone (-) or MBP fused to the Tudor or
750 Tudor-UDR fragments of 53BP1. The asterisk (*) labels bands that we attribute as possible
751 protein degradation products. **e**, the various MBP proteins used in the pulldown assays were
752 separated by SDS-PAGE and stained with Coomassie brilliant blue. **f**, Competition assay in
753 which the GST-UbvG08 was prebound to the MBP-Tudor fusion of 53BP1. Increasing amounts
754 of a synthetic peptide derived from the region of H4K20me2 were added. After extensive
755 washing, bound proteins were analyzed by immunoblotting against GST and MBP. **g**, Isothermal
756 titration calorimetry profiles obtained by titration of UbvG08 (squares) or UbvG08-DM (circles)
757 titrated into a solution of the 53BP1 Tudor protein. Curves were fitted with a one-set-of-sites
758 model. The dissociation constant (K_d) for the UbvG08-53BP1 interaction is indicated.

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760 **Figure 2. Structure of the UbvG08 bound to the 53BP1 Tudor domain.** **a**, Ribbons
761 representation of the UbvG08 (shown in green) – 53BP1 Tudor domain (shown in gold)

762 complex. The hydrophobic patch centered on I44 of the UbvG08 structure is highlighted in red.
763 **b**, Reciprocal interaction surfaces on UbvG08 (top) and 53BP1 Tudor domain (bottom). Contact
764 residues are highlighted on their respective surfaces. **c**, Zoom-in of the UbvG08-53BP1 Tudor
765 domain contact region. Hydrogen and salt interactions are denoted by black dotted lines. **d**, MBP
766 pulldown assay of GST fused to ubiquitin (Ub) or to the indicated UbvG08 proteins, with the
767 MBP-53BP1-Tudor protein. **e**, MBP-pulldown assay of GST fused to UbvG08, its L70V mutant
768 or the indicated Ub proteins, with the MBP-53BP1-Tudor protein. **f**, MBP-pulldown assay of
769 GST fused to ubiquitin (Ub) or to the indicated UbvG08 proteins, with the MBP-53BP1-Tudor
770 protein. PD, pulldown. IB, immunoblot.

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772 **Figure 3. The i53 protein inhibits 53BP1 and activates gene conversion. a-b**, U2OS cells
773 were transfected with vectors expressing i53, its 53BP1-binding deficient mutant (DM) or an
774 empty vector (EV) control. Cells were then X-irradiated with a 10 Gy dose and processed for
775 immunofluorescence with the indicated antibodies 1 h post-irradiation (IR). DAPI staining (not
776 shown) was used to delineate the outline (dashed lines) of the cell nuclei. The region in the
777 magnified inset is indicated with a square. Quantitation of the experiment is shown in panel (a)
778 where each circle is a biological replicate and the bar is at the mean ($N=3$), whereas in (b)
779 representative micrographs are shown. Arrowheads indicate Flag-positive cells. Additional
780 micrographs are shown in [Supplementary Fig. 3a](#). **c**, Parental or *53BP1Δ* U2OS cells transfected
781 with vectors expressing i53, the DM mutant or an empty vector (EV) control were irradiated (2
782 Gy) 1 h before being processed for immunofluorescence. Cell cycle stage was assessed by
783 Cyclin A staining. Each circle represents a biological replicate and the bar is at the mean; $N=3$.
784 Micrographs are shown in [Supplementary Fig. 3b](#). **d**, Immunoprecipitation (IP) of Flag-tagged

785 proteins from extracts prepared from 293T cells transfected with vectors expressing Flag-i53 or
786 the i53-DM mutant. Proteins were separated by SDS-PAGE and immunoblotted (IB) for Flag
787 and 53BP1. **e**, Schematic of the DR-GFP assay. **f**, U2OS DR-GFP were first transfected with
788 siRNAs targeting the *53BP1* or *BRC1* mRNAs along with a non-targeting siRNA (CTRL). 24 h
789 post-transfection, cells were transfected with the I-SceI expression vector and the percentage of
790 GFP-positive cells was determined 48 h post-I-SceI transfection for each condition. The values
791 were normalized to the CTRL siRNA condition. Each point is a biological replicate and the bar
792 is at the mean \pm s.e.m; $N=4$. **g**, U2OS DR-GFP cells were transfected with the vectors
793 expressing i53, the DM mutant or an empty vector control (EV) along with an I-SceI expression
794 vector. The percentage of GFP-positive cells was determined 48 h post- transfection for each
795 condition and was normalized to the empty vector condition. Each point is a biological replicate
796 and the bar is at the mean \pm s.e.m; $N=4$. **h**, U2OS DR-GFP cells were transfected with either an
797 empty vector (EV) or vectors expressing Flag-tagged i53 or the DM mutant along with an I-SceI
798 expression vector. Cells were treated either with DMSO (-) 1 μ M SCR7 or 1 μ M of the SCR7
799 pyrazine analog (pyrSCR7). The percentage of GFP-positive cells was determined 48 h post-
800 transfection for each condition and was normalized either to the EV (left) or DM (right)
801 conditions. Each point is a biological replicate and the bar is at the mean \pm s.e.m ($N=3$ for all
802 experiments on the left graph, except for SCR7+DM and SCR7+i53 where $N=2$; $N=4$ for all
803 experiments on the right graph).

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805 **Figure 4. Stimulation of HDR by i53 with dsDNA and ssODN donors.** **a**, Gene targeting
806 efficiency at the *LMNA* locus^{16, 23} in parental or *53BP1* Δ U2OS cells following transfection with
807 vectors expressing Flag-tagged i53 or its DM mutant or an empty vector control (EV). The

808 DNA-PK inhibitor NU7441 was also added where indicated. 24 h post-transfection, cells were
809 analysed for mClover fluorescence. Individual experiments are presented along with the mean
810 +/- s.d., ($N=3$). **b**, Mono- and bi-allelic gene targeting at the *HIST1HB2K* locus²⁴ in K562 cells
811 previously transduced with AAV coding for i53 or i53-DM (DM). The *HIST1HB2K-mAG* and
812 *HIST1HB2K-mCherry* donors were introduced by nucleofection at the same time as a Cas9 RNP
813 targeting *HIST1HB2K*. Control reactions where 72 h post-transfection, cells were analysed for
814 mAG and mCherry fluorescence. Individual experiments are presented along with the mean +/-
815 s.d., ($N=3$). **c**, Gene targeting efficiency at the *Hsp90a1* locus in mouse embryo fibroblasts
816 previously transduced with AAV coding for i53 or i53-DM (DM). The *Hsp90a1-t2A-ZsGreen*
817 template vector was introduced by transfection at the same time as the vector coding for the
818 sgRNA and Cas9. 8 days post-transfection, cells were analysed for ZsGreen fluorescence.
819 Individual experiments are presented along with the mean +/- s.d., ($N=3$). **d**, HDR at the *CCR5*
820 locus²⁶ in K562 cells where ZFN mRNA and an XhoI inserting *CCR5* donor (*CCR5**) were first
821 nucleofected. 24 h later, cells were either left untreated (control) or nucleofected with increasing
822 concentrations of i53 mRNA or i53-DM (DM) mRNA. 24 h later, cells were collected and gene
823 targeting was determined by RFLP analysis. Individual experiments are presented along with the
824 mean +/- s.d., ($N=3$). **e**, BFP-to-GFP conversion by ssODN-mediated HDR in 293T cells
825 previously transduced with AAV coding for i53 or i53-DM (DM). An optimal ssODN donor
826 targeting GFP (*GFP-I*)³⁰ and Cas9 RNP were then nucleofected and 96 h post-transfection, cells
827 were analysed for GFP and BFP expression. Individual paired experiments are presented. **f, g**,
828 HDR at the *CCR5* and *CXCR4* loci in 293T (f) and K562 (g) cells previously transduced with
829 AAV coding for i53 or i53-DM (DM). ssODN donor targeting *CCR5* (*CCR5[#]*) or *CXCR4*
830 (*CXCR4[#]*)³⁰ and Cas9 RNP were then nucleofected and 72 h post-transfection, editing was

831 determined by RFLP analysis. Individual paired experiments are presented on the left graphs
832 whereas the relative editing efficiency is presented in the right graphs where data is presented as
833 the mean +/- s.d., ($N=4$ for f and $N=3$ for g). **h**, BFP-to-GFP conversion by ssODN-mediated
834 HDR in 293T cells was carried out as panel e with the exception that cells were either transfected
835 with a non-targeting siRNA (siCTRL), a pool of siRNAs targeting CtIP (siCtIP (pool)) or a
836 different, custom-designed siRNA targeting CtIP (siCtIP-5). Individual experiments are
837 presented along with the mean +/- s.d., ($N=3$).

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